

The Information System of Environmental Conservation Department

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Abstract. The Information System of Environmental Conservation Department is designed to provide timely and accurate information related to environmental conservation efforts and policies. The system targets government departments, environmental professionals, students, local communities, and the general public. In many parts of the world, especially in developing countries, awareness and engagement in environmental issues such as deforestation, pollution, waste management, and climate change are growing. This platform supports the sharing of timely updates, awareness campaigns, best practices, and early warnings about environmental hazards. Ensuring access to reliable information, combined with education and community participation, is vital for promoting sustainable development and protecting natural resources for future generations.

Keywords: awareness, climate, conservation, deforestation, environment, environmental hazards, pollution

INTRODUCTION

Many people, especially in developing countries, are often unaware of the importance of protecting the environment. With busy daily lives, many individuals are not well-informed about the issues of the environment or the steps they can take to help. Lack of education about topics such as waste management, water conservation, and sustainable practices leads to more harm to nature. This project aims to address these gaps by providing an easy-to-use system that educates people about environmental issues and offers practical solutions that can help preserve the environment for future generations. This system is designed to offer a wide range of information about the environmental conservation in a simple and accessible way. The system will be user-friendly, making it easy for people to find the information they need to take action in their daily lives. The goal is to quickly and effectively provide users with the knowledge they need to make informed decisions that contribute to a healthier planet.

PROBLEM

The Environmental problems such as pollution, illegal logging, climate change, and poor waste management are becoming more severe in our society. Many people, especially those in rural areas and young students, lack access to reliable and easy-to-understand environmental information. Without proper knowledge and awareness, communities often continue harmful practices that damage the environment and public health. A clean and

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sustainable environment is essential for the well-being of all living things, and protecting the nature is everyone's responsibility. Through this system, the users can easily access accurate information and become more involved in solving the environmental problems.

APPROACH

This system consists of two roles: Administrator and User. On the user side, the users can view the main page, read the updating news, give the comments under the news, read about the department and responsibilities, view related departments, and see the contact page. The contact page has been added so that the users can easily contact the admin when needed. If the users want to give feedback to the department, the users must be entering their name, email, title and subject in the contact_form. Then, the users must to click 'send' button, and the system will stop working.

On the administrator side, the admin must be log in first. And then, the admin (or) staff can view the dashboard of system. Moreover, the admin can also upload and view the categories, contents and enquiries. The admin not only update categories, contents and enquiries but also delete and edit categories, contents and enquiries. The admin can see and reply the comments of the users who use this system, filter the news added to the system as a monthly report, reply to messages sent by the users and also add or delete staff to post news in the system and update staff login information.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram uses data modeling techniques that can help define business processes and serve as the foundation for a relational database. An ERD attribute can be denoted as a primary key, which identifies a unique attribute, or a foreign key, which can be assigned to multiple attributes. A cardinality notation can then define the attributes of the relationship between entities. In the database, there are five data tables for the administrator and the user. The tables are categories, comment, contact_form, contents and system_user. The figure 2 shows database design for all the data tables and their relationship of the database.

RESULTS

Each page of the Information System of Environmental Conservation Department has been carefully and simply designed. In this system, the users can see the main page for department, easily read the news about the department and responsibilities of the department, give the comment under the news, and know how to contact the department with just having the internet on the user's mobile phone or other devices without logging in. If the users are in the place where there is no internet, the fact that the users cannot use this system will be a disadvantage. Therefore, we will continue to work hard to make it easier in the future and even in the places where there is no internet. This system is a place where the users can directly connect online instead of going to the department. Mainly, this system can help the users to get the right information about the environmental conservation.

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Figure 3: Home Page

Figure 4: System Report

CONCLUSION

This system is implemented for the Environmental Conservation Department under the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environmental Conservation (Hinthada Township). This system is a vital component in supporting public awareness and engagement regarding environmental issues. It ensures timely, accurate, and accessible information related to environmental protection, conservation activities, climate change updates, public announcements, and educational campaigns. The information system can significantly improve the communication between the department and the public by delivering updates on environmental policies, ongoing projects, local and national conservation events, and

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community-based environmental programs. Public environmental education and outreach campaigns are essential to raise awareness of the importance of environmental protection. In conclusion, developing and implementing the Information System of Environmental Conservation Department is essential to achieving long-term conservation goals and building an environmentally conscious society for the future.

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